

Innovation of environmental friendly agricultural technology supporting sustainable food self-sufficiency

Andi. M. Syakir

Head of Indonesian Agency for Agricultural Research and Development

Jl. Ragunan 29 Pasar Minggu Jakarta Selatan 12540, Indonesia

Self-sufficiency of rice, shallots, and chili were reached in 2016, self-sufficiency of corn were achieved in 2017, and soybean is targeted on 2020. Even since 2016, Indonesia has no longer import any commodities such as rice (medium-class rice), fresh chili, and shallots. In 2017, Indonesia has stop corn inportation, meaning that we save about 10,6 billion rupiah of foreign exchange.

The achievement of production and self-sufficiency also have an impact on the welfare of farmers. Self-sufficiency of rice, shallots, and chili were reached in 2016, self-sufficiency of corn were achieved in 2017, and soybean is targeted on 2020. Even since 2016, Indonesia has no longer import any commodities such as rice (medium-class rice), fresh chili, and shallots. In 2017, Indonesia has stop corn inportation, meaning that we save about 10,6 billion rupiah of foreign exchange. Indonesia is proved by exporting 7.561 tons of shalloots to Thailand, Malaysia, and Timor Leste. The increase of such crop productivity is due to the innovation of technology such as pest resistance of high-yielding variety, balanced fertilizer application, agricultural machinery utilization, water and soil management, and synergy collaboration between farmers, government, privates, stakeholder and other components. The number of prosperous farmers household has increased from 85.2% in March 2014 to 85.87% household in March 2017.

The poverty in rural areas also decline. In March 2017, the poor population in rural areas becomes 17,10 million people decrease 842 thousand peopleor 4,7% compared to March 2015as many as 17,94 million people. The gini ratio in the rural areas improved, in March 2017 by 0,320 decrease by 0,014 point or 4,19% compared to March 2016 by 0,334. Based on evaluation result from The Economist Intelligence Unit (EIU), in 2017 Indonesia ranks 69 of 113 countries for food security, rank 64th of 76 for aspect of food availability, while ranks 21th out of 25 countries for food sustainability index.

The effort to achieve and mantain self-sufficiency requires crop production facilities that are supportive and enviromentally friendly. In the future, the achievement of agricultural development is not only measured by production-success as known as food-sufficiency but also measured by food quality and food safety. Food safety is an important global issue to be concidered to enter world free market. In the future, the challenges of

agricultural development will be more difficult and need serious attention from all parties.

In the year 2020, we will enter the eras of global market that prioritize the balance of natural work naturally so as not damage the environment. All the traded product must meet the specified standards in order to be accepted in the global market. The product listed must met in terms of security. So that, Indonesia product acceptable in world trade. We react them by implementing environmentally friendly agricultural cultivation with various appropriate technological innovation, sustainable, integrated, which is packed with approaches of integrated crop management, system of rice intensification, cultivation- based on super planting-distance, low external input supply agriculture (LEISA), organic farming, climate smart agriculture, and conservation agriculture.

In the past decades, environmental issues have contributed to sustainable agricultural development, including global warming and climate change, degradation of agricultural land resource and a decrease of environmental quality including pollution of agrochemical material in soil, water and agricultural products. Global warming has become serious issues that attract world attention. Global warming is due to an increase of concentration and emission of anthropogenic greenhouse gases which affect climate change and threaten food insecurity. On the other hand, agricultural sector is regarded as the source GHGs emissions at the same time. Therefore, cultivation practice requires innovation and technology in effort to decrease global warming impacts.

The green revolution technology that has been agricultural basis must be transformed into bio-revolution in an effort to increase productivity of agricultural crops while maintaining environmental quality. Cultivation activities in effort to increase production should be done wisely and appropriately. Usage of excessive agrochemical material (inorganic fertilizer, pesticides) by farmer solely to achieve the expected production. The use of these chemical material can reduce quality of agricultural product in terms of security. Usage of excess agrochemical material can pollute environmental and increase contamination in soil and plants. In the past decades, environmental issues have contributed to sustainable agricultural development, including global warming and climate change, degradation of agricultural land resource and a decrease of environmental quality including pollution of agrochemical material in soil, water and agricultural products. Global warming has become serious issues that attract world attention. Global warming is due to an increase of concentration and emission of anthropogenic greenhouse gases which affect climate change and threaten food insecurity. On the other hand, agricultural sector is regarded

as the source GHGs emissions at the same time. Therefore, cultivation practice requires innovation and technology in effort to decrease global warming impacts.

Indonesia has committed to reduce national GHGs emissions. Based on President Regulation 61/2011 and Intended Nationally Determined Contributions (INDC, 2015), reduction of GHGs emission is 29% reduction with own efforts in 2030 or 41% reduction if received financial and technological support from industrialized countries. In the last decade, global warming is an environmental issue which becomes serious attention by local, regional, global societies. Global warming occurs due to the increase of concentration and emission of greenhouse gas (GHGs) in atmosphere. Climate change impacts significantly in agricultural sector which threaten food security. However, agricultural sector also is source of main GHGs such as carbon dioxide, methane, and nitrous oxide. Methane is produced by anaerobic decomposition of organic matter which occur in rice cultivation, biomass burning, enteric fermentation, and manure management. While nitrous oxide is produced as intermediate product in microbial nitrification-denitrification processes which occur in nitrogen fertilization, agricultural land, manure management.

General Policy of Agricultural Sector:

Adaptation action program as a top priority to secure food for all Indonesian people. Mitigation action program supports National Action Plan of GHG emission reduction and can be done through the development of environmentally friendly technology innovation. Mitigation can be implemented as long as it does not sacrifice production and as long as it can be done in synergy with mitigation

The next step after innovation is its implementation of applied environmental-friendly agricultural technology. Strategy of improve agriculture environment are needed. Remediation of agrochemical contaminations is an effort to reduce contaminant or pollution from agricultural land. There are some remediation using innovation technology, e.g. amelioration, bio-remediation, and phyto-remediation. Besides that, improving regulation and governmental policy could suppress inappropriate agrochemical material uses.

Amelioration is a technology to increase soil fertility while could absorb toxic compounds in soil and reduce pesticide residue in soil and water. Dry compost, activated charcoal (rice husk, coconut shell) have high iodine absorption and could absorb insecticide residue (aldrin, lindane, heptachlore, dieldrin and chlorpyrifos). Dry manure, dry compost, rice husk charcoal, and coconut shell charcoal have iodine absorption as much as 223, 312, 406, 1192 % (Ardiwinata et al, 2005). Application of cattle manure, household waste and peat

from Rawa Pening could decrease Cd in rice straw. Tea waste, zeolite and cattle manure could also reduce in Cd in rice.

Technology of urea coated by either active charcoal or biochar can increase nitrogen use efficiency while reduce pesticide residue in soil. Urea coated biochar is a slow release material so that nutrient is more effective absorbed by plant to fit its requirement. Also surface and porous charcoal can fix heavy metals and pesticide residue. Existence of pores in charcoal provides ideal habitat for some microbes including degradation bacteria. Bioremediation is a part of environmental biotechnology which utilizes microbial activity to degrade dangerous contaminants to materials with less toxicity or no toxic. The certain microbial use for remediation decrease effectively pesticide residue in rice field.

The use of dissolved phosphate bacteria could reduce carbofuran in the soil by 99,6%. *Pseudomonas mallei* dan *Trichoderma*, sp. could reduce insecticide residue of organochlorine (dieldrin, endosulfan, DDT dan heptachlor). Bacteria could also increase in effectivity of urea coated by biochar and reduce in hexa chlorobenzene and aldrin by 33,1% and 33,6%, respectively. Urea coated active charcoal from corn ear enriched by degrading pesticide microbes can reduce residues of dieldrin and aldrin as much as 55.6% and 49.3%, respectively (Sri Wahyuni et al., 2015). The use of UAC enriched consorsia microbes can remediate residues of heptachlor, DDT in soil as much as 71% and 94%, respectively.

Reduce Water Contaminant by Filter inlet-outlet in irrigation canal. Contaminants in irrigation water should be filtered to minimize their residues before entering in the field. Filter contained biochar from agricultural wastes can be lain on inlet-outlet canals. There are some strategies to anticipate climate change impact in agricultural sector, e.g. adaptation action as main priority to stabilize food security, Mitigation action as co benefit of adaptation saction through development of agricultural technology with environmental friendly, Adaptation action should be synergic with mitigation action to achieve target of agricultural development (production and economy). Adaptation actions in agricultural sector are rice cultivation using adapted rice varieties (drought or flood resistance rice varieties); application integrated Crop Calendar; improvement of irrigation canal, water harvester and water pumping; encourage environmental friendly agriculture; improvement of soil physic to increase infiltration and water holding capacity by using organic matters.

Mitigation of GHGs emission can be done through water management, plant management, land management/amelioration, and integrated livestock-crop systems. Methane emission from intermittent irrigation was lower than continuous flooding (Setyanto dan Abubakar, 2006). Intermittent irrigation

could increase rice production by 5-9% than continuous flooding (Pramono et al., 2015). Integrated livestock-food crop system (ILCS) is an approach that synergy between adaptation action with mitigation actions on climate change impacts. The ILCS improve productivity of soil, plant and livestock, improve soil fertility, provide renewable energy, and reduce in GHG emission, particularly methane (CH₄) and nitrous oxide (N₂O).

Releasing methane emission from rice paddy depend on characteristic of rice varieties such as character, plant period and root activity. Planting system was also influence to GHG emission and rice yield, where direct seeded systems provides rice yield around 76% higher than transplanting system and reduce 21.6% of methane emission (Wihardjaka, 2011).

The ICM approach generally produces lower GHG emission. The ICM integrates some technologies such as high yielding variety, young seedling, intermittent irrigation, organic matter and recommended chemical fertilizer. The application of amelioration materials improves soil fertility and reduce GHGs emission, e.g. dolomite, zeolite, manure, rice husk, household waste (tea, coffee), turmeric rhizome and weed. Use of weed *Ageratum conyzoides* combined with 100% NPK could reduce N₂O emission around 12%.

Integrated Livestock and Crops:

Improvement of soil, plant and livestock productivity

Improvement soil fertility

Provide renewable energy

Reduce in GHG emission, particularly CH₄ dan N₂O

Strengthening the implementation of regulations related to the supervision of pesticide distribution and pesticide use, as well as strict food safety. The government must be strict in supervising, monitoring, and calculating the circulation of pesticides, especially those that have been banned, organochlorine compounds that are toxic, persistent, and bio accumulative. The government is also expected to actively monitor the impact of pesticide residues on agricultural commodities and their production processes.

IPM was successfully implemented in 1997, but is currently weak in its implementation. Strengthening the program and concept of IPM in improving the quality and quantity of agricultural products, supported by the progress of extensive biological pesticide development, including the use of biological agents, vegetable pesticides. Therefore, the existing IPM concept needs to be revitalized, enhanced in capacity, must do more simple, and supported by a strong institutional system.

Development of environmental-friendly agricultural technology is include of organic agriculture. The role of government in the development of organic agriculture, organic farming requires investment in capacity building, farmers' skills, institutional strengthening and infrastructure development. In addition, the rules and incentives issued by the government can be a driver for the growth of organic agricultural production.

With the policies of the central and regional governments, it will foster the independence of organic farmers with the development of facilities / infrastructure and the development of organic product certification institutions as well as strengthening supporting institutions such as farmer groups, extension agents, and marketing institutions. Development of environmental-friendly agricultural technology that include of organic agriculture, adaptation and mitigation technology to climate change.

Conclusions

Application of environmentally friendly technology should give high production while maintain environmental quality. The available technology with environment friendly must be delivered and adopted farmers and user. Dissemination of upstream-downstream environmentally friendly technology with a socio-ecological approach should be strived continuously . This event is of important relating to issues presented earliar. By saying Bismillahi rohmanir rohim. I officialy open this workshop and semir. I hope through this workshop and seminar we could compile ideas and thoughts from expert and researcher that can be an input for sustainability of Indonesian agricultural development.